

Project: “Analysis of the spreading of Cobid-19 in North Africa Countries

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<i>day</i>	<i>Algeria</i>	<i>Egypt</i>	<i>Morocco</i>	<i>Tunisia</i>
<i>1 June</i>	9319	23988	8045	1058
<i>2 June</i>	9448	24890	8108	1059
<i>3 June</i>	9574	25813	8168	1059
<i>4 June</i>	9697	26757	8226	1059
<i>5 June</i>	9819	27720	8283	1060

Infected

<i>day</i>	<i>Algeria</i>	<i>Egypt</i>	<i>Morocco</i>	<i>Tunisia</i>
<i>1 June</i>	596	877	199	47
<i>2 June</i>	597	890	199	47
<i>3 June</i>	599	903	200	47
<i>4 June</i>	600	915	200	47
<i>5 June</i>	601	927	200	47

deaths

<i>day</i>	<i>Algeria</i>	<i>Egypt</i>	<i>Morocco</i>	<i>Tunisia</i>
<i>1 June</i>	5470	6105	5998	1361
<i>2 June</i>	5883	6307	6172	1369
<i>3 June</i>	6025	6510	6345	1376
<i>4 June</i>	6168	6715	6519	1384
<i>5 June</i>	6310	6921	6693	1391

hospitalizations

<i>day</i>	<i>Algeria</i>	<i>Egypt</i>	<i>Morocco</i>	<i>Tunisia</i>
<i>9 June</i>	7029	9020	7770	962
<i>10 June</i>	7176	9325	7963	962
<i>11 June</i>	7323	9634	8156	962
<i>12 June</i>	7470	9946	8348	962
<i>13 June</i>	7615	10262	8539	962

hospitalizations

<i>day</i>	<i>Algeria</i>	<i>Egypt</i>	<i>Morocco</i>	<i>Tunisia</i>
<i>9 June</i>	725	1137	202	47
<i>10 June</i>	733	1155	202	47
<i>11 June</i>	741	1173	203	47
<i>12 June</i>	748	1190	203	47
<i>13 June</i>	755	1209	203	47

deaths

<i>day</i>	<i>Algeria</i>	<i>Egypt</i>	<i>Morocco</i>	<i>Tunisia</i>
<i>9 June</i>	10435	35877	8378	1066
<i>10 June</i>	10457	37280	8422	1067
<i>11 June</i>	10657	38719	8464	1067
<i>12 June</i>	10764	40196	8504	1067
<i>13 June</i>	10869	41710	8544	1067

infected

Day	Infected	Hospitalizations	Deaths
14 June	1071	1082	48
15 June	1072	1089	48
16 June	1072	1096	48
17 June	1072	1103	48
18 June	1072	1109	48
19 June	1072	1115	48

Table 4: Tunisia

Day	Infected	Hospitalizations	Deaths
14 June	8621	8269	205
15 June	8658	8431	205
16 June	8693	8591	205
17 June	8727	8750	205
18 June	8759	8908	205
19 June	8790	9063	205

Table 3: Morocco

Day	Infected	Hospitalizations	Deaths
14 June	44345	11607	1575
15 June	46042	12017	1620
16 June	47783	12435	1666
17 June	49568	12859	1711
18 June	51400	13289	1757
19 June	53277	13725	1802

Table 2: Egypt

Day	Infected	Hospitalizations	Deaths
14 June	10906	7666	775
15 June	11005	7806	783
16 June	11102	7944	791
17 June	11197	8082	800
18 June	11288	8218	808
19 June	11378	8353	816

Table 1: Algeria

Day	Infected	Hospitalizations	Deaths
21 June	1160	1020	50
22 June	1168	1024	50
23 June	1176	1027	51
24 June	1184	1031	51
25 June	1192	1035	51
26 June	1199	1038	51

Table 4: Tunisia

Day	Infected	Hospitalizations	Deaths
21 June	56311	14814	2193
22 June	58251	15283	2279
23 June	60233	15758	2365
24 June	62259	16239	2451
25 June	64328	16726	2537
26 June	66441	17218	2623

Table 2: Egypt

Day	Infected	Hospitalizations	Deaths
21 June	9942	8282	214
22 June	10146	8355	214
23 June	10350	8429	214
24 June	10554	8503	215
25 June	10758	8576	215
26 June	10962	8650	215

Table 3: Morocco

Day	Infected	Hospitalizations	Deaths
21 June	11605	8527	847
22 June	11689	8655	859
23 June	11771	8781	870
24 June	11851	8905	882
25 June	11929	9028	894
26 June	12005	9150	905

Table 1: Algeria

Day	Infected	Hospitalizations	Deaths
05 July	15891	11438	953
06 July	16287	11753	961
07 July	16684	12068	969
08 July	17080	12383	977
09 July	17476	12698	985
10 July	17872	13012	993

Table 1: Algeria

Day	Infected	Hospitalizations	Deaths
05 July	75437	20905	3290
06 July	76860	21386	3376
07 July	78283	21869	3462
08 July	79706	22353	3549
09 July	81129	22839	3638
10 July	82552	23326	3727

Table 2: Egypt

Day	Infected	Hospitalizations	Deaths
05 July	14072	9660	234
06 July	14394	9736	235
07 July	14716	9811	237
08 July	15037	9884	238
09 July	15359	9955	240
10 July	15680	10024	241

Table 3: Morocco

Day	Infected	Hospitalizations	Deaths
05 July	1188	1049	50
06 July	1190	1053	50
07 July	1193	1056	50
08 July	1196	1060	50
09 July	1199	1063	50
10 July	1201	1066	50

Table 4: Tunisia

Day	Infected	Hospitalizations	Deaths
12 July	19184	13608	1013
13 July	19646	13910	1021
14 July	20108	14211	1030
15 July	20570	14512	1039
16 July	21032	14813	1048
17 July	21493	15114	1057

Table 1: Algeria

Day	Infected	Hospitalizations	Deaths
12 July	82135	24274	3898
13 July	83108	24762	3989
14 July	84080	25250	4080
15 July	85053	25739	4173
16 July	86026	26229	4266
17 July	86998	26718	4360

Table 2: Egypt

Day	Infected	Hospitalizations	Deaths
12 July	15764	12431	248
13 July	15997	12778	250
14 July	16230	13124	252
15 July	16463	13470	253
16 July	16696	13816	255
17 July	16929	14162	257

Table 3: Morocco

Day	Infected	Hospitalizations	Deaths
12 July	1260	1077	50
13 July	1271	1082	50
14 July	1281	1087	50
15 July	1292	1093	50
16 July	1302	1098	50
17 July	1312	1104	50

Table 4: Tunisia

Day	Infected	Hospitalizations	Deaths
19 July	23090	16095	1078
20 July	23663	16439	1088
21 July	24235	16783	1098
22 July	24808	17127	1108
23 July	25380	17471	1118
24 July	25953	17815	1128

Table 1: Algeria

Day	Infected	Hospitalizations	Deaths
19 July	87971	28013	4443
20 July	88772	28516	4533
21 July	89573	29019	4623
22 July	90375	29521	4714
23 July	91176	30022	4805
24 July	91977	30523	4897

Table 2: Egypt

Day	Infected	Hospitalizations	Deaths
19 July	17210	14958	272
20 July	17431	15274	275
21 July	17652	15590	278
22 July	17874	15907	281
23 July	18095	16223	284
24 July	18317	16539	287

Table 3: Morocco

Day	Infected	Hospitalizations	Deaths
19 July	1364	1101	50
20 July	1376	1102	50
21 July	1387	1103	51
22 July	1398	1104	51
23 July	1410	1105	51
24 July	1421	1106	51

Table 4: Tunisia

Day	Infected	Hospitalizations	Deaths
26 July	27364	18166	1157
27 July	27980	18463	1169
28 July	28597	18760	1180
29 July	29213	19057	1192
30 July	29829	19353	1203
31 July	30446	19650	1214

Table 1: Algeria

Day	Infected	Hospitalizations	Deaths
26 July	92192	33693	4603
27 July	92810	34531	4644
28 July	93429	35370	4686
29 July	94047	36208	4727
30 July	94666	37046	4768
31 July	95284	37885	4810

Table 2: Egypt

Day	Infected	Hospitalizations	Deaths
26 July	19987	16496	312
27 July	20445	16717	318
28 July	20903	16937	324
29 July	21361	17157	330
30 July	21819	17378	337
31 July	22277	17598	343

Table 3: Morocco

Day	Infected	Hospitalizations	Deaths
26 July	1451	1140	50
27 July	1463	1147	50
28 July	1476	1155	50
29 July	1488	1162	50
30 July	1501	1169	50
31 July	1513	1177	50

Table 4: Tunisia

Day	Infected	Hospitalizations	Deaths
02 August	31527	21406	1233
03 August	32110	21841	1245
04 August	32692	22277	1256
05 August	33275	22713	1268
06 August	33857	23149	1280
07 August	34440	23584	1291

Table 1: Algeria

Day	Infected	Hospitalizations	Deaths
02 August	94645	42308	4872
03 August	94983	43587	4907
04 August	95321	44866	4943
05 August	95659	46145	4979
06 August	95997	47425	5015
07 August	96335	48704	5050

Table 2: Egypt

Day	Infected	Hospitalizations	Deaths
02 August	25729	18298	378
03 August	26562	18582	389
04 August	27395	18867	399
05 August	28228	19151	410
06 August	29060	19436	421
07 August	29893	19720	431

Table 3: Morocco

Day	Infected	Hospitalizations	Deaths
02 August	1568	1222	51
03 August	1587	1233	51
04 August	1606	1244	51
05 August	1625	1255	51
06 August	1644	1266	51
07 August	1663	1277	51

Table 4: Tunisia

Day	Infected	Hospitalizations	Deaths
09 August	35207	24521	1303
10 August	35744	24953	1314
11 August	36281	25385	1325
12 August	36818	25817	1335
13 August	37355	26249	1346
14 August	37893	26681	1357

Table 1: Algeria

Day	Infected	Hospitalizations	Deaths
09 August	95456	53097	5011
10 August	95597	54576	5031
11 August	95738	56055	5051
12 August	95879	57534	5071
13 August	96020	59013	5091
14 August	96161	60492	5112

Table 2: Egypt

Day	Infected	Hospitalizations	Deaths
09 August	33159	23013	496
10 August	34333	23720	512
11 August	35506	24428	528
12 August	36680	25136	544
13 August	37854	25843	559
14 August	39028	26551	575

Table 3: Morocco

Day	Infected	Hospitalizations	Deaths
09 August	1700	1264	51
10 August	1723	1271	51
11 August	1746	1278	51
12 August	1769	1285	51
13 August	1792	1292	51
14 August	1814	1299	51

Table 4: Tunisia

Day	Infected	Hospitalizations	Deaths
16 August	38608	27012	1370
17 August	39088	27360	1380
18 August	39568	27707	1389
19 August	40048	28055	1399
20 August	40528	28402	1408
21 August	41008	28750	1418

Table 1: Algeria

Day	Infected	Hospitalizations	Deaths
16 August	96481	59814	5163
17 August	96613	60805	5184
18 August	96745	61796	5205
19 August	96876	62787	5225
20 August	97008	63778	5246
21 August	97140	64769	5267

Table 2: Egypt

Day	Infected	Hospitalizations	Deaths
16 August	42319	29274	657
17 August	43729	30088	681
18 August	45139	30902	706
19 August	46548	31716	730
20 August	47958	32530	754
21 August	49367	33344	778

Table 3: Morocco

Day	Infected	Hospitalizations	Deaths
16 August	2073	1349	54
17 August	2140	1365	54
18 August	2206	1380	54
19 August	2273	1396	54
20 August	2339	1411	54
21 August	2406	1426	54

Table 4: Tunisia

Day	Infected	Hospitalizations	Deaths
23 August	41471	29170	1435
24 August	41877	29471	1444
25 August	42284	29773	1453
26 August	42690	30074	1462
27 August	43096	30376	1471
28 August	43502	30677	1480

Table 1: Algeria

Day	Infected	Hospitalizations	Deaths
23 August	97371	66017	5259
24 August	97494	66899	5274
25 August	97617	67782	5289
26 August	97741	68664	5304
27 August	97864	69546	5319
28 August	97987	70429	5334

Table 2: Egypt

Day	Infected	Hospitalizations	Deaths
23 August	52245	36191	888
24 August	53721	37259	923
25 August	55197	38327	958
26 August	56673	39395	993
27 August	58148	40463	1028
28 August	59624	41531	1063

Table 3: Morocco

Day	Infected	Hospitalizations	Deaths
23 August	2832	1445	71
24 August	2937	1460	74
25 August	3042	1474	77
26 August	3146	1488	80
27 August	3251	1502	83
28 August	3355	1516	86

Table 4: Tunisia

Day	Infected	Hospitalizations	Deaths
06 September	46384	32745	1555
07 September	46695	32995	1563
08 September	47005	33245	1571
09 September	47316	33495	1578
10 September	47627	33744	1586
11 September	47938	33994	1594

Table 1: Algeria

Day	Infected	Hospitalizations	Deaths
06 September	99910	78057	5531
07 September	100077	78914	5549
08 September	100244	79770	5567
09 September	100411	80626	5585
10 September	100578	81482	5602
11 September	100745	82339	5620

Table 2: Egypt

Day	Infected	Hospitalizations	Deaths
06 September	71976	55167	1364
07 September	73594	56423	1400
08 September	75213	57679	1437
09 September	76832	58935	1474
10 September	78450	60192	1510
11 September	80069	61448	1547

Table 3: Morocco

Day	Infected	Hospitalizations	Deaths
06 September	4997	1747	94
07 September	5200	1774	96
08 September	5403	1801	99
09 September	5606	1829	102
10 September	5809	1856	105
11 September	6012	1883	108

Table 4: Tunisia

Day	Infected	Hospitalizations	Deaths
13 September	48274	34058	1614
14 September	48541	34233	1622
15 September	48808	34407	1631
16 September	49075	34581	1639
17 September	49342	34756	1648
18 September	49609	34930	1656

Table 1: Algeria

Day	Infected	Hospitalizations	Deaths
13 September	101022	84153	5645
14 September	101181	85010	5662
15 September	101340	85867	5679
16 September	101500	86724	5697
17 September	101659	87580	5714
18 September	101819	88437	5731

Table 2: Egypt

Day	Infected	Hospitalizations	Deaths
13 September	86545	67788	1582
14 September	88704	69789	1614
15 September	90864	71789	1645
16 September	93023	73790	1676
17 September	95183	75791	1707
18 September	97342	77792	1739

Table 3: Morocco

Day	Infected	Hospitalizations	Deaths
13 September	6747	2005	108
14 September	7026	2039	110
15 September	7305	2073	112
16 September	7584	2108	115
17 September	7863	2142	117
18 September	8142	2176	120

Table 4: Tunisia

Day	Infected	Hospitalizations	Deaths
20 September	49845	35071	1675
21 September	50067	35211	1683
22 September	50289	35350	1692
23 September	50511	35490	1700
24 September	50733	35629	1709
25 September	50955	35769	1717

Table 1: Algeria

Day	Infected	Hospitalizations	Deaths
20 September	102039	89469	5769
21 September	102179	90217	5787
22 September	102318	90965	5805
23 September	102458	91712	5823
24 September	102597	92460	5841
25 September	102737	93208	5859

Table 2: Egypt

Day	Infected	Hospitalizations	Deaths
20 September	101787	80792	1829
21 September	104103	82754	1865
22 September	106419	84715	1901
23 September	108735	86677	1937
24 September	111052	88639	1973
25 September	113368	90601	2009

Table 3: Morocco

Day	Infected	Hospitalizations	Deaths
20 September	10030	2405	150
21 September	10512	2437	156
22 September	10993	2468	162
23 September	11475	2499	167
24 September	11957	2530	173
25 September	12439	2561	179

Table 4: Tunisia

Day	Infected	Hospitalizations	Deaths
27 September	51088	35872	1717
28 September	51262	35985	1723
29 September	51437	36098	1728
30 September	51611	36211	1734
01 October	51786	36324	1740
02 October	51960	36437	1745

Table 1: Algeria

Day	Infected	Hospitalizations	Deaths
27 September	102852	95106	5884
28 September	102971	95906	5900
29 September	103089	96706	5916
30 September	103207	97505	5932
01 October	103325	98305	5948
02 October	103444	99105	5964

Table 2: Egypt

Day	Infected	Hospitalizations	Deaths
27 September	117565	95862	2071
28 September	120003	97809	2107
29 September	122441	99756	2144
30 September	124879	101704	2181
01 October	127317	103651	2217
02 October	129756	105598	2254

Table 3: Morocco

Day	Infected	Hospitalizations	Deaths
27 September	15751	5599	206
28 September	16563	6166	214
29 September	17375	6733	222
30 September	18187	7300	230
01 October	18999	7867	238
02 October	19811	8434	246

Table 4: Tunisia

Day	Infected	Hospitalizations	Deaths
04 October	52148	36586	1762
05 October	52303	36689	1769
06 October	52458	36792	1776
07 October	52613	36896	1783
08 October	52768	36999	1790
09 October	52923	37103	1797

Table 1: Algeria

Day	Infected	Hospitalizations	Deaths
04 October	103694	97577	5983
05 October	103817	97874	5997
06 October	103940	98171	6010
07 October	104063	98468	6024
08 October	104186	98765	6037
09 October	104309	99062	6051

Table 2: Egypt

Day	Infected	Hospitalizations	Deaths
04 October	133382	110859	2332
05 October	135793	113034	2368
06 October	138203	115209	2404
07 October	140614	117384	2440
08 October	143025	119559	2475
09 October	145435	121734	2511

Table 3: Morocco

Day	Infected	Hospitalizations	Deaths
04 October	21899	5032	307
05 October	22853	5032	321
06 October	23808	5032	335
07 October	24763	5033	348
08 October	25718	5033	362
09 October	26673	5033	376

Table 4: Tunisia

Day	Infected	Hospitalizations	Deaths
11 October	53070	37221	1800
12 October	53205	37311	1807
13 October	53340	37401	1813
14 October	53474	37491	1819
15 October	53609	37581	1825
16 October	53744	37670	1831

Table 1: Algeria

Day	Infected	Hospitalizations	Deaths
11 October	104513	97833	6050
12 October	104634	97933	6060
13 October	104756	98033	6070
14 October	104877	98133	6081
15 October	104999	98234	6091
16 October	105120	98334	6101

Table 2: Egypt

Day	Infected	Hospitalizations	Deaths
11 October	152440	127423	2608
12 October	155464	129783	2648
13 October	158489	132144	2688
14 October	161513	134504	2728
15 October	164538	136865	2768
16 October	167562	139225	2808

Table 3: Morocco

Day	Infected	Hospitalizations	Deaths
11 October	32166	5032	478
12 October	34001	5032	506
13 October	35837	5032	534
14 October	37672	5032	562
15 October	39508	5032	591
16 October	41343	5032	619

Table 4: Tunisia

Day	Infected	Hospitalizations	Deaths
25 October	56137	39081	1914
26 October	56395	39228	1922
27 October	56654	39375	1931
28 October	56912	39522	1939
29 October	57170	39669	1947
30 October	57429	39816	1955

Table 1: Algeria

Day	Infected	Hospitalizations	Deaths
25 October	106556	98954	6199
26 October	106725	99070	6210
27 October	106893	99185	6222
28 October	107061	99300	6233
29 October	107229	99416	6245
30 October	107397	99531	6256

Table 2: Egypt

Day	Infected	Hospitalizations	Deaths
25 October	197769	163045	3306
26 October	201481	165864	3362
27 October	205194	168683	3417
28 October	208906	171502	3473
29 October	212619	174321	3529
30 October	216331	177140	3584

Table 3: Morocco

Day	Infected	Hospitalizations	Deaths
25 October	49279	5033	827
26 October	50287	5034	851
27 October	51295	5034	874
28 October	52304	5035	898
29 October	53312	5035	921
30 October	54321	5036	945

Table 4: Tunisia

Day	Infected	Hospitalizations	Deaths
01 November	58263	40363	1973
02 November	58572	40551	1981
03 November	58881	40739	1990
04 November	59190	40927	1998
05 November	59499	41114	2007
06 November	59809	41302	2015

Table 1: Algeria

Day	Infected	Hospitalizations	Deaths
01 November	107726	99603	6279
02 November	107897	99716	6290
03 November	108068	99830	6301
04 November	108239	99943	6312
05 November	108410	100057	6323
06 November	108581	100171	6335

Table 2: Egypt

Day	Infected	Hospitalizations	Deaths
01 November	222880	184232	3760
02 November	226690	187327	3823
03 November	230500	190421	3887
04 November	234310	193516	3951
05 November	238120	196610	4015
06 November	241929	199705	4079

Table 3: Morocco

Day	Infected	Hospitalizations	Deaths
01 November	60837	5032	1370
02 November	62434	5033	1436
03 November	64031	5033	1503
04 November	65629	5033	1569
05 November	67226	5033	1636
06 November	68824	5033	1702

Table 4: Tunisia